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A variant in CYP2R1 predicts circulating vitamin D levels after supplementation with high-dose of vitamin D in healthy adolescent girls

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Abstract

Aim: The determinants of serum vitamin D seems to be the environmental factors (dietary and supplementary intake and exposure to ultraviolet light) and genetic factors. We aimed to study the relationship between a vitamin D-associated genetic polymorphism and serum 25(OH)D concentrations in healthy adolescent girls in Iran, and its effects on a high-dose supplement of vitamin D. **Material and method:** A total of 616 healthy adolescent girls with mean age 15 received 50,000 IU of vitamin D3 weekly over 9 weeks. Serum vitamin D levels and other metabolic factors were measured at baseline and after the intervention. The genotyping of the CYP2R1 variant (rs10741657) was performed by TaqMan genotyping assays. **Results:** Regardless of the genetic background, at baseline, 87% of adolescent girls were vitamin D deficient (serum 25(OH)D level < 50 nmol/l). High-dose supplementation with VitD reduced the proportion of girls who were deficient substantially to about 24%. The genetic analysis revealed that although at baseline there was not a gene-vitamin D association (p trend = 0.1), the response to supplementation appeared to be modulated by this variant (p trend < 0.001). However, other anthropometric and biochemical measures were not affected by this intervention, over this short period. Serum 25(OH)D was increased in all participants although the carriers of the minor A allele seemed to be better responders so that the percentages of the change serum vitamin D in the holder of AA and AG genotypes were 539.4 ± 443.1 and 443.7 ± 384.6 , respectively, compared with those with common GG genotype (363.3 ± 354.0). Our regression analysis revealed that the probability of an increase in serum 25(OH)D in a participant with AA genotype was 2.5-fold greater than those with a GG genotype (OR = 2.5 (1.4–4.4); p value = 0.002). **Conclusion:** Based on our findings, it appears that the rs10741657 variant of the CYP2R1 gene modulates the response to high-dose of vitamin D supplementation.

Keywords: CYP2R1, rs10741657, supplementation, vitamin D.